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Synthesis and Characterisation of Mixed Heteropoly Molybdotungstotellurate

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SYNTHESIS of ammonium salts as well as free acids of the 6-heteropoly anion^{1,2} of general formula $[\text{NiMo}_{6-n}\text{W}_n\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_6]^{4-}$ and some mixed 12-heteropoly anions, involving successive replacement by pentavalent vanadium in molybdophosphoric acid has been reported by Tsigdinos *et al.*³. Solution phase studies of this class of compounds have been done exhaustively by Spitsyn *et al.*⁴. Niobium, like vanadium can also replace molybdenum in the heteropoly anion $[\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]^{3-}$. A molybdovanadoselenious acid of composition $\text{H}_6[\text{SeMo}_{10}\text{V}_2\text{O}_{40}]\cdot\text{X}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been prepared by etheral extract and partially characterised⁵. Heteropoly anion of general formula $[\text{XZW}_{11}\text{O}_{40}\text{H}_2]^{2-}$, where X=Si, Ge or P and Z=Co^{II}, Co^{III} or Ni^{II} have been prepared⁶. In view of these reports, it appeared worthwhile to investigate the replacement of molybdenum by tungsten in 6-heteropoly molybdotellurate anion $[\text{TeMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$, which is well characterised^{7,8}.

Experimental

Solutions of K_2WO_4 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{WO}_4$ were prepared from $\text{WO}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ using KOH and NH_4OH , respectively. Complete and stoichiometric reaction was determined by absence of precipitate and a final pH of ~8.

Sodium 5-molybdo 1-tungstotellurate: A homogeneous aqueous solution of 400 ml of molybdic acid was prepared by dissolving 9.90 g $\text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 100 ml water by heating for 5 to 6 h at 80° with occasional stirring. To that hot solution an aqueous solution of 100 ml $\text{H}_2\text{TeO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.30 g) were added gradually with stirring followed by addition of 100 ml solution of NaNO_3 (3.06 g). The pH of the solution was adjusted at 2.5 to 3.5 by adding 12 ml glacial acetic acid. It was refluxed for 3 h at 90°.

The volume of the total solution was reduced to 100 ml and left for crystallisation. After 10 days, bright glassy crystals were collected, recrystallised from hot water and washed with 90% ethanol to yield the product (70%) (Found: Na, 8.50; Te, 7.5; W, 11.36; Mo, 29.86; H_2O , 17.90. $\text{Na}_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. Na, 8.61; Te, 7.99; W, 11.48; Mo, 29.96; H_2O , 17.97%).

Potassium 5-molybdo 1-tungstotellurate: Synthesis was carried out as above by substituting potassium tungstate for sodium tungstate. Large glassy prismatic crystals obtained after 12 days of studying were recrystallised from hot water and washed with 95% ethanol to yield the product (95%) (Found: K, 14.26; Te, 7.73; W, 11.20; Mo, 29.44; H_2O , 13.19. $\text{K}_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. K, 14.39; Te, 7.87; W, 11.31; Mo, 29.52; H_2O , 13.28%).

Ammonium 5-molybdo 1-tungstotellurate: Using ammonium tungstate in place of sodium tungstate and following the same procedure for preparation as above, large glassy crystals of the compound were collected after 9 days (70%) (Found: N, 4.91; Te, 7.50; W, 10.83; Mo, 28.46; H_2O , 23.46. $(\text{NH}_4)_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 22\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. N, 5.00; Te, 7.61; W, 10.95; Mo, 28.57; H_2O , 23.57%).

The percentage of water in the compounds was determined by heating the samples around 500° to constant weight. Sodium and potassium were estimated⁹ by zinc uranyl acetate and tetraphenyl borate methods, respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by elemental analysis. Molybdenum and tungsten were estimated⁹ by precipitating out simultaneously with α -benzoinoxime. Tellurium was estimated gravimetrically⁹ as elementary tellurium by reducing it with sodium-hypophosphite.

Infrared spectra: The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Peaks at 3350 to 3450 and 1610 to 1630 cm^{-1} regions are for lattice water¹⁰. Other peaks are at 320 to 325 and 685 to 690 cm^{-1} for Te-O in octahedral co-ordination¹¹, 900-1000 cm^{-1} due to M-O and 725-850 cm^{-1} for M-O-M (M=Mo or W) bridging².

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of $\text{K}_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in solutions at pH 2.5 and 5 were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 202 spectrophotometer. The intense absorption at 260 nm may be due to charge transfer from oxygen to molybdenum (or tungsten), as shown by heteropolytungstate, in the uv region¹².

Thermal stability: The studies on thermal stability of these heteropoly compounds were conducted by TGA, DTA and by heating at fixed temperature followed by solubility determinations of the heated materials to ascertain decomposition. All the experiments were carried out under nitrogen at a heating rate of 5° min^{-1} . Replacement of one of the six MoO_6 octahedra by a WO_6 octahedron in the heteropoly anion $[\text{TeMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$ does not lead to any significant change in the thermal

behaviour of the salts of mixed heteropoly anion $[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$. The dehydrated salts exist upto 250° after which they are completely decomposed. Insolubility in water of the heated samples, also show the decomposition of the heteropoly salts.

Molecular weight determination: The molecular weight of $\text{Na}_6[\text{TeWMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was cryoscopically determined to be 1301 ± 250 in $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ system by the method as applied by Thilo and Kruger¹⁸ and recently by Pope¹⁴. The cryoscopic constant was taken¹⁴ as 1.8 ± 0.1 kg of water per mole.

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Study of Solvent Effect on Kinetics of Alkaline Hydrolysis of Methylsalicylate in Water-Acetone Medium

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A number of papers¹⁻¹⁰ have appeared concerning changes in the rates of hydrolysis of esters in binary solvent mixtures. Some of them^{2,3} have supported the views expressed by Parker⁴ about the rate enhancement by aprotic solvent constituent of the binary solvent system. However, this view has been strongly refuted by some authors^{1,5,6,8,9} and they observed decrease in the hydrolysis rate by several aprotic solvents. In the present paper an attempt has been made to study the effect of medium

(water-acetone) on the alkali catalysed hydrolysis of methyl salicylate.

Experimental

Methyl salicylate and acetone of B.D.H. and E. Merck L.R. grade were used and purified by the known procedure. Preparation of solution and other experimental procedure are the same as previous communications^{9,11}. The specific rate constants were determined in different solvent mixtures containing 10 to 70% acetone (v/v) at temperatures ranging 15 to 35° (Table 1). The reliability of k values were found to be $\pm 0.1 \times 10^{-2}$.

Results and Discussion

The hydrolysis of methylsalicylate follows the $B_{AC} 2$ mechanism in Ingold's terminology¹². According to this mechanism, the rate controlling step is addition of OH^- ion to carbonyl carbon¹³. The transition state of the rate controlling step will not only be polar but will have two units of negative charges superimposed on it. The formation of such transition states in case of the above ester hydrolysis must be favoured by increasing dielectric constant of the medium. Therefore, the rate should fall with increasing percentage of acetone whose dielectric constant is much smaller than water. This is in conformity of the experimental observation (Table 1). The decrease in rate with

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS (k) IN WATER-ACETONE MEDIA
 $k \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$

Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	Acetone% (v/v)						
	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
15	10.2	8.7	7.0	5.7	5.0	4.5	4.2
20	20.4	16.7	13.8	10.6	9.1	8.4	7.9
25	40.3	31.8	24.8	20.0	17.3	15.7	13.6
30	75.0	60.3	49.6	37.8	31.8	27.9	24.1
35	141.3	116.1	88.1	66.7	60.8	50.7	44.2

increasing mole percent of organic co-solvent of low dielectric constant has been observed by Anantkrishnan *et al.*¹⁰. They have noted that in a medium of dielectric constant higher than 10, solvent solute interaction is more influencing a factor than the dielectric constant. It can therefore be concluded that the observed decrease in rate in water-acetone medium is the combined effect of decrease in dielectric constant as well as solvation changes.

Activation energy: The activation energy value (E_a , shown in Table 2) decreases with increasing

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION ENERGY (E_a) VALUES

Acetone% (v/v)	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
E_a (k cal mol ⁻¹)	23.1	22.6	22.2	21.7	21.3	21.1	20.8